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FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF D.C.C.BANKS IN TAMIL NADU

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The author made an attempt to study performance of DCCBs in Tamil Nadu taking into account selected financial indicators viz., deposits, loans and advances and overdues of DCCBs for a period of seven years (1998-99 to 2004-05). Analysis revealed that deposits, loans and advances exhibited positive growth.

Introduction

The Co-operative Credit Societies Act passed in 1904 provided for organising co-operative credit societies in rural areas. It was then realised that central organisations should be formed for assisting and guiding the primary societies. Accordingly, the Central Government enacted Co-operative Societies Act in 1912 which provided for the formation of central organisations. Then Central Banks were formed at district level, to which primary societies were affiliated. Following the recommendations of the All India Rural Credit Survey Committee (1954), the structure of the Central Cooperative banks was rationalised and central cooperative banks were reorganized and strengthened into viable institutions.

The central co-operative banks occupy a crucial position in the pyramidal structure of agriculture cooperative credit system in a state. They form the backbone of the structure; and provide the vital link between the local primary societies and the state cooperative bank organised at the state level. They act as balancing centres and provide funds to the primary societies located in rural areas in the district when they face shortage by diverting the surplus funds. They mobilise resources by accepting deposits and by borrowing from the State Cooperative Bank. They provide facility for the investment of the resources of primary societies. They develop and extend banking facilities in semi-urban areas besides rural areas. They also supervise and guide the working of the member societies in the district. There are at present 23 Central Cooperative Banks serving 31 districts in Tamil Nadu including the newly created Ariyalur district.

This paper attempts to focus on the trend and growth of selected financial indicators for the state as a whole, taking into account the parameter of all the DCCBs individually including profitability. DCCBs in Tamil Nadu have experienced fluctuating profit during 1998-99 to 2004-05 which is shown in Table 1.

It is evident from Table 1 that year after year the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu have shown profits in aggregation. The number of profit making DCCBs are lower than the loss making ones. The quantum of profits is also higher than the loss made by the DCCBs in the state. This has obvious implications on the overall viability and sustainability of the middle tier cooperative credit structure in Tamil Nadu. It is interesting to know that all banks have recorded profit in 2005.

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Methodology

Compound growth rates were estimated for the selected financial indicators. An exponential function of the following type was employed to estimate the growth rates.

$$Y = ab^t$$

Where,

Y= indicators

a= constant term

b= regression co-efficient (rate of change in Y per unit change in year)

t= number of years

Annual compound growth rate in percentage

$r = (b-1) 100$

b= antilog of $r/100$

Growth of deposits

The Central Cooperative Banks accept various kinds of deposits from individuals, cooperatives and other institutions. The reserve fund and surplus funds of the cooperative societies are deposited with the concerned central cooperative banks. The voluntary agencies like local bodies, societies incorporated under the Societies Registration Act, Universities and Technical institutions, Government Corporations, companies owned wholly by Government, Religious/Charitable Institutions, Educational institutions, Electricity Board, regulated markets etc. have been directed by the State Government to keep their funds with the Central Cooperative Bank. Table 2 shows the trend and growth rates of deposits over the study period.

It could be seen from Table 2 that the annual growth rate of deposits in the D.C.C.Banks in Tamil Nadu is positive in all the banks except in Tirunelveli. The fitted regression model Tirunelveli is insignificant. The co-efficient of determination in the above case indicates that the change in the amount of deposits is only to the extent of 0.94%. Insignificant annual growth rates are seen in Kumbakonam, Madurai, Nilgiris, Salem, Sivagangai, and Thoothukudi banks with 8.26, 1.56, 1.25, 30.13, 6.77 and 1.04 times respectively. The fitted trend equation in the above said cases are insignificant at 5% level. The compound growth rate is positive in all the banks except in Tirunelveli which has a negative growth rate of - 0.38%.

Growth of loans and advances

The position of loans and advances outstanding in respect of short-term loans, cash credits, and overdrafts and bill purchased and discounted, medium-term loans conversion, rephasements/rescheduled loans in jewel loans to individuals are presented in the Table 3.

It could be seen from Table 3 that annual growth rates of loans and advances outstanding in D.C.C. Banks in Tamil Nadu are positive in all the banks. Growth rates are statistically significant in all banks except in Dharmapuri bank. It indicates that there is an increase in the amount of loans and advances outstanding during Dharmapuri bank. The fitted regression model for trend equation in Dharmapuri is insignificant. The co-efficients of determination in all banks are higher than 0.90 except in Dharmapuri, Tirunelveli and Thoothukudi banks with 0.44, 0.89 and 0.84 times respectively.

Growth of overdue position

Overdues have been a major problem at primary society level as member cultivators of agricultural credit societies do not repay the loans borrowed from the societies on the due date owing to various reasons such as political interference, crop failures etc. Primary societies in turn fail to repay their loans to the Central Cooperative Banks, causing heavy overdues. The trend and growth of overdue position is presented in Table 4.

Overdues of D.C.C.Banks show negative annual growth rates in Nilgiris, Sivagangai, Thanjavur, and Virudhunagar banks with -0.76, -0.11, -0.17 and -0.30 times respectively. It shows that the amount of overdues in the above banks have declined during the study period. But the decline is not statistically significant. There are positive annual growth rates in all other banks are statistically significant at 5% level only in Chennai, Kancheepuram, Ramanathapuram, Salem, and Thiruchirappalli banks. The fitted trend equations in above cases are also significant. This shows that the problem of overdues is very much felt by the five banks in Chennai, Kancheepuram, Ramanathapuram, Salem and Thiruchirappalli. These banks should take special initiatives to recover the dues.

Summary of findings

Annual growth rates of deposits in the DCCBs in Tamil Nadu are positive in all the banks except in Tirunelveli bank. All DCCBs in Tamil Nadu showed a positive annual growth rates in loans and advances. The total overdues of DCCBs in Tamil Nadu revealed a negative annual growth rates in Nilgiris, Sivagangai, Thanjavur, and Virudhunagar banks.

Table 1: Profit/loss of D.C.C.Banks in Tamil Nadu (1998-99 to 2004-05)

S.N.	Particulars	1998-99	1999-00	2000-01	2001-02	2002-03	2003-04	2004-05
1	Profit	35.40	37.54	53.02	82.63	92.96	99.16	349.84
2	No.of Banks	16	10	10	15	13	14	23
3	Loss	11.86	55.52	68.87	66.52	132.37	255.86	-
4	No.of Banks	7	10	13	8	10	9	-
5	Audit not completed	-	3	-	-	-	-	-
6	Total banks	23	23	23	23	23	23	23

Source: Compiled from the Annual Report of TNSAC Bank Ltd., Chennai (1998-99 to 2004-05)

Table 2: Trend and growth of deposits in D.C.C.Banks in Tamil Nadu

S.N.	Name of D.C.C.Bank	Trend co-efficient		R ²	F	CGR (%)
		a	b			
1	Chennai	577.66	87.87*	0.9207	58.03	10.73
2	Coimbatore	295.58	11.01*	0.6319	8.58*	3.47
3	Cuddalore	90.81	43.68*	0.6917	11.54*	37.00
4	Dharmapuri	196.36	11.36*	0.6247	8.32*	5.27
5	Dindigul	179.02	10.84*	0.8164	22.24*	5.21
6	Erode	262.69	10.88*	0.7056	11.98*	3.78
7	Kancheepuram	271.69	12.70*	0.5899	7.19*	4.22
8	Kanyakumari	76.38	13.78*	0.7826	18.00*	11.86
9	Kumbakonam	214.41	8.26	0.4029	3.37	3.65
10	Madurai	382.56	1.56	0.0045	0.023	0.51
11	Nilgiris	90.73	1.25	0.0924	0.51	1.45
12	Pudukkottai	107.17	10.07*	0.8363	25.55*	7.49
13	Ramanathapuram	121.98	9.12*	0.8497	28.27*	6.23
14	Salem	650.28	30.13	0.5174	5.36	4.29
15	Sivagangai	119.05	6.77	0.4186	3.60	5.32
16	Thanjavur	119.82	4.51*	0.5849	7.05*	3.54
17	Tiruchirappalli	338.11	20.84*	0.8395	26.14*	5.28
18	Tirunelveli	190.71	-0.94*	0.0094	0.05	-0.38
19	Tiruvannamalai	101.40	13.98*	0.9256	62.18*	9.95
20	Thoothukudi	126.47	1.04	0.0283	0.15	0.87
21	Vellore	215.87	12.39*	0.7425	14.42*	5.09
22	Villupuram	151.25	26.07*	0.9341	70.84	11.73
23	Virudhunagar	178.54	8.74*	0.6655	9.95*	4.38

*Significant at five percent level

Table 3: Trend and growth of loans and advances in D.C.C.Banks in Tamil Nadu

S.N.	Name of D.C.C.Bank	Trend co-efficient		R ²	F	CGR (%)
		a	b			
1	Chennai	294.40	96.66*	0.9535	102.45*	16.48
2	Coimbatore	165.42	30.34*	0.9612	123.93*	11.98
3	Cuddalore	118.97	33.16*	0.9791	234.62*	14.43
4	Dharmapuri	386.40	24.92	0.4446	4.00	5.99
5	Dindigul	129.16	26.74*	0.9944	892.36*	12.35
6	Erode	153.05	20.66*	0.9856	341.73*	9.40
7	Kancheepuram	242.76	23.26*	0.9350	71.86*	7.41
8	Kanyakumari	90.82	19.71*	0.9424	81.81*	12.17
9	Kumbakonam	215.92	14.89*	0.9040	47.10*	5.52
10	Madurai	295.30	25.69*	0.9810	258.17*	6.69
11	Nilgiris	57.96	8.73*	0.9179	55.86*	10.66
12	Pudukkottai	100.17	20.69*	0.9821	274.48*	12.17
13	Ramanathapuram	98.98	16.02*	0.9442	84.66*	10.20
14	Salem	261.54	53.57*	0.9858	384.69*	12.19
15	Sivagangai	118.44	15.76*	0.9727	178.37*	9.32
16	Thanjavur	132.55	15.21*	0.9516	98.36*	8.13
17	Tiruchirappalli	212.55	51.34*	0.9919	608.83*	13.67
18	Tirunelveli	94.21	12.61*	0.8929	41.69*	9.49
19	Tiruvannamalai	151.16	22.83*	0.9850	329.37*	9.99
20	Thoothukudi	80.52	8.55*	0.8456	27.39*	8.04
21	Vellore	146.04	36.92*	0.9427	82.23*	14.73
22	Villupuram	211.98	32.09*	0.9163	54.75*	9.70
23	Virudhunagar	97.63	14.97*	0.9483	91.76*	9.91

*Significant at five percent level

Table 4: Trend and growth of overdues in D.C.C.Banks in Tamil Nadu

S.N.	Name of D.C.C. Bank	Trend co-efficient		R ²	F	CGR (%)
		a	b			
1	Chennai	8.49	0.91*	0.6211	8.19*	7.60
2	Coimbatore	16.59	9.34	0.3669	2.90	19.45
3	Cuddalore	8.61	4.55	0.2892	2.03	16.38
4	Dharmapuri	-18.89	29.72	0.3336	2.50	91.22
5	Dindigul	23.33	4.28	0.3230	2.39	10.06
6	Erode	-0.80	8.36	0.2999	2.14	39.25
7	Kancheepuram	24.72	7.62*	0.8306	24.52*	16.29
8	Kanyakumari	9.98	0.63	0.0708	0.38	6.89
9	Kumbakonam	46.08	3.58	0.0905	0.49	3.26
10	Madurai	32.23	4.76	0.4356	3.86	9.70
11	Nilgiris	28.93	-0.76	0.0292	0.15	-1.58
12	Pudukkottai	33.07	3.12	0.1074	0.60	4.29
13	Ramanathapuram	23.38	4.04*	0.7486	14.89*	10.18
14	Salem	3.34	8.21*	0.7399	14.23*	29.15
15	Sivagangai	38.92	-0.11	0.0003	0.0013	-2.97
16	Thanjavur	62.32	-0.17	0.0004	0.0019	-2.19
17	Tiruchirappalli	8.35	6.92*	0.7017	11.76*	24.05
18	Tirunelveli	13.63	0.24	0.0633	0.34	1.39
19	Tiruvannamalai	40.81	2.06	0.1982	1.23	4.75
20	Thoothukudi	10.83	0.52	0.1224	0.70	3.56
21	Vellore	-5.05	11.64	0.4842	4.69	36.14
22.	Villupuram	24.07	3.25	0.5525	6.17	9.33
23	Virudhunagar	18.58	-0.30	0.0262	0.13	-3.34

*Significant at five percent level

